

SHRINKAGE DEFECT MODELING IN THERMOSET COMPOSITES

Vladimir Korotkov, Yurii Chekanov, Boris Rozenberg
Department of Polymers and Composites
Institute of Chemical Physics in Chernogolovka
Chernogolovka, Moscow region, 142432, Russia

ABSTRACT

Shrinkage defects of different types can develop during isothermal cure of thermosets in three-dimensionally constrained conditions. These conditions can exist on the microscale in composites with high content of reinforcement. The regularities of shrinkage defect formation in different temperature ranges, influence of relaxational transitions in polymer matrix during curing, scale and form factors are discussed. Results of experimental modeling are analyzed on the basis of theoretical estimations of shrinkage stresses, taking into account influence of the diffusion control due to vitrification on the cure kinetics. A nonisothermal cure schedule was developed to decrease shrinkage defect formation.

INTRODUCTION

During manufacturing of thermoset composites, matrix undergoes, in a general case, two relaxational transitions, gelation and vitrification. These transitions lead to abrupt, up to several orders of magnitude, change of viscoelastic and strength properties and make it difficult to simulate mechanical phenomena accompanying the curing of composites. The relaxational transitions during isothermal curing can be conveniently shown with time-temperature-transformation (TTT) cure diagram developed last decade [1]. A very interesting mechanical event during cure is the process of defect formation under internal stresses. Internal stresses on the microscale can arise due to different change of the specific volume of composite components during manufacturing. Study of the defect development allows, from one hand, to investigate the process of the matrix mechanical property formation, and, from the other, to elucidate the relationships between manufacturing conditions and final properties of composites.

During composite manufacturing thermosetting matrix can be viscous fluid with sol liquid structure, high elastic (sol-gel rubber), and elastic (sol or sol-gel glass). Mechanical properties of the matrix are very different in the each stage and conditions of shrinkage defect development are different as well. The cause the defects can be both thermal and chemical shrinkage.

Isothermal conditions will be considered first. Thermal strains do not develop at a constant temperature, but chemical shrinkage of curing matrix is constrained by the reinforcement and can cause internal stresses. In the liquid state, shrinkage stresses are defined by the rate of shrinkage and the viscosity of the matrix and they are negligible.

In the rubbery state, the situation is quite different, when the matrix is under one- or two-dimensional constraints, and under three-dimensional constraints [2,3]. In the first case, chemical shrinkage is compensated by rubber like deformation, which can develop in the epoxies up to tens of percents. The maximum rubber modulus, E_r^∞ , is about 30 MPa for epoxies. The maximum volumetric chemical shrinkage, ε_c^∞ , is about 5%. Not above 30% of the total shrinkage take place in a solid, rubbery or glassy, state: $\varepsilon_s^\infty \approx .3\varepsilon_c^\infty$. Maximum shrinkage stresses are small, $\sigma \approx E_r^\infty \varepsilon_s^\infty \approx .5$ MPa. In three-dimensionally constrained conditions, the rubber like strain does not develop and the bulk modulus is quite high, $K_r^\infty \approx 1.5$ GPa [2,4]. Then, maximum stresses can reach significant value, $\sigma \approx K_r^\infty \varepsilon_s^\infty \approx 20$ MPa. Such stresses are above the matrix strength in the rubbery state and can cause defect formation during cure.

In the glassy state, enormous disparity between one- or two-dimensional constrains and three-dimensional constraints disappears. The bulk modulus is about the tensile modulus, $K_g \approx E_g \approx 3$ GPa, and $\sigma \approx K_g \varepsilon_s^\infty \approx E_g \varepsilon_s^\infty \approx 50$ MPa is about the strength in the glassy state. Defects can arise, especially when the thermosetting matrix is not deeply in the glassy state.

One- and two-dimensionally constrained conditions more often take place in practice and these are usually considered. It has led to the opinion about dominant importance of the cooling stage for shrinkage defect occurring, when the glassy state takes place. In some cases three-dimensionally constrained conditions are possible. Then shrinkage stresses in the rubbery state should be taken into consideration as well as in the glassy state.

Three-dimensionally constrained conditions can take place on the microscale in polymer composites with high fiber content. The transversal stiffness of reinforcement increases abruptly while approaching the maximum fiber content [5], and the reinforcement forms a kind of a rigid shell on the microscale around the curing matrix. Bulk properties of thermosets relevant for three-dimensionally constrained conditions have been investigated poor, especially during curing. That hinders to simulate shrinkage defect formation and causes to use previously experimental modeling. In this paper, the authors' investigations of shrinkage defects in thermosets relevant to composites are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three models were developed, which allow to observe visually the process of defect formation under three-dimensionally constrained conditions during thermoset curing, [3,6]. The long tube model is a glass tube filled with a curing system with a length which is a few tens times as large as the inner diameter of the tube. In the radial direction, the model can be considered absolute rigid. After transition from the liquid state into the rubbery or the glassy state, three-dimensionally constrained conditions take place at some distance from the free ends. The ratio of the mean distance between cohesive shrinkage defects to the inner diameter was proposed as a shrinkage cracking parameter.

The shorter tube the stronger effect of the end free surfaces is. The stress level is significantly less even in the center of tubes with a relative length about ten. There it a length, such that for shorter tubes shrinkage defects do not arise at all. The ratio of this length to the inner diameter is another parameter of shrinkage cracking. Short samples of the curing system were obtained by incorporation of air gaps dividing a long tube into several independent samples.

A plate model was proposed to investigate influence of another geometry. Two plate glasses were separated by a thin paper spacer, to prevent approach of the plates in the transversal direction under shrinkage stresses. The stiffness of the model can not be considered as absolute.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate the relationship between relaxation transitions and shrinkage defect formation, isothermal cure of epoxy-amine systems in the long tube model was carried in different temperature regions with consideration of the TTT-diagram and a model of shrinkage stress development. In order to estimate the level of shrinkage stresses in a long tube during isothermal cure, the next model was considered. The stresses were calculated due to incremental elasticity [7], because the bulk modulus does not relax in time [8]:

$$\sigma(t) = \int_{\alpha_s}^{\alpha} K_s d\varepsilon_s \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_s = \varepsilon_c^{\infty} (\alpha - \alpha_s) \quad (2)$$

where K_s is the bulk modulus and ε_s is the volume shrinkage in the solid state, α is the conversion, α_s is the conversion at the moment of solidification due to vitrification or gelation. The bulk modulus was considered to be different in the rubbery state, 1.5 GPa, and in the glassy state, 3 GPa. The conversion of the curing matrix was calculated taking into account kinetic control of the reaction before vitrification and diffusion control then [9].

Shrinkage stresses for different cure times are shown in Fig. 1. Three states are noted: sol glass, gel glass and rubber. These states differ both network structure and intermolecular interaction. The authors do not have reliable data concerning the bulk strength in these states during cure, but one can assert that the strength strongly varies both between states and in the scope of a state. In the glass gel state, the curing system is the most strength. In the rubbery state and in the sol glass state, the bulk strength is much less. Four ranges of temperature differing in shrinkage defect formation can be discerned.

Fig. 1. Isochrones of shrinkage stresses.

The most simple case is curing above the glass transition temperature of completely cured polymer, T_g^∞ . In this case, vitrification does not occur during cure, and gelation is the only transition that the system experiences. Shrinkage stresses developed in the rubbery state are higher than low values of the strength in the state, and cohesive shrinkage defects arise in the region, Fig. 2.

Figure. 2. Shrinkage defects developed during curing above T_g^∞ .

There are strong adhesion interaction between epoxy resin and the glass tube, and only cohesive defects develop initially. A similar situation likely to take place in glass fiber composites. When a cohesive defect reaches the wall of the tube, it develops further as an adhesive debonding. After a certain time, when debondings and cohesive defects spread over the entire length of the tube, excluding small regions near the free ends, any visible development of the fracture process ceases.

In the temperature range lower than T_g^∞ , shrinkage defects occurred in the rubbery state are entirely similar to the defects above T_g^∞ . However, at the moment of vitrification, abrupt increase in the strength terminates defect development.

In the next, intermediate temperature range, vitrification occurs immediately after gelation, which is the cause of solidification. Vitrification is a quite wide transition. The intermediate range embraces temperatures, where effect of vitrification on the strength hinders defect formation in the rubbery state. There are few shrinkage defects and their appearance differs significantly from the appearance in the high temperature ranges [10], Fig. 3. Adhesive debondings does not develop because cohesive defects do not reach the walls of the tube due to their small dimensions.

Figure. 3. Shrinkage defects developed during curing in the intermediate temperature range.

In the low temperature range, lower T_g^{gel} , vitrification is the cause of solidification. The strength of the system in the sol glassy state is not high and there are many defects of different types [11].

The intermediate temperature range is the most interesting one to produce composite materials because of the form and sparsity of shrinkage defects developing in the long tube model. However, it is impossible to achieve complete cure in the range, because after vitrification the rates of cure reactions become very low. Therefore, a part of cure should be carried in a higher temperature range and a nonisothermal cure was considered. A nonisothermal cure in constrained conditions causes temperature stresses brought about by the difference of thermal expansion coefficients of the glass and the resin. The complete cure regime includes a stage of heating up to a maximum temperature and a stage of cooling down to room temperature. The cooling causes tension stresses, which are dangerous. The heating stage can partly compensate both chemical shrinkage and thermal one during cooling [2]. It is desirable to accumulate maximum compression stresses during heating. So, solidification should be realized at a minimum possible temperature. Such a temperature is in the intermediate range. In this range, the liquid-rubber transition does not actually cause shrinkage defect development. Besides, possible shrinkage defects in this range are small and their form is the least dangerous one [12]. After this transition, increase in temperature leads to accumulation of compressive stresses. The increase should be carried up to the temperature allowing to achieve necessary degree of cure.

The regime proposed was realized. Cohesive shrinkage defects have not arisen, but small debondings developed during cooling were observed [13]. The long tube model can be used to try a cure regime for the trend to shrinkage defect formation and to optimize it.

Investigation of thermoset cure in the long tube model elucidates mechanical behavior of thermoset during cure under three-dimensional constraints. The behavior of thermoset matrix in composite can differ because there are obvious distinctions between composites and the model: scale, form and stiffness of a rigid shell. To investigate these factors additional experiments are necessary. For two epoxy-amine systems, observations were carried for tubes of different inner diameters [6]. The range investigated spreads from 15 microns up to 7 mm. The mean relative distances between shrinkage cracks were measured. The results are shown in Fig. 4. The influence of the scale factor is negligible nearly over three orders of magnitude and shrinkage defects can take place on the scale of the matrix thickness in composites.

Fig. 4. Relative mean distance between defects.

The short tube model and the plate model allow to investigate defect formation in less absolute conditions. Influence of free ends decreases level of shrinkage stresses in the short tube model and delays defect emergence [3]. Above T_g^∞ , new defects arise up to complete conversion as the length of short specimens decreases. Below T_g^∞ , new defects arise only up to vitrification. Different form of the plate model changes significantly appearance of shrinkage defects (Fig. 5), but close study shows similarity of the defect development process to the one in the tube model [6].

Figure. 5. Debondings and cohesive defects developed during curing in the plate model.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The following directions are very topical after the research described. Influence of the volume content and structure of reinforcement on the shrinkage defect formation is not known. Both theoretical simulation and sophisticated experimental modeling could provide further progress.

Influence of shrinkage defects on final properties of composite is not always obvious. This concerns, first of all, the strength properties. Microdefect development unloads residual stresses and can decrease brittleness of the composite. Influence of different types of cohesive defects and debondings developed in different temperature ranges can strongly differ.

Possibility to control defect formation was demonstrated. It is necessary now to determine composite performance criteria which present shrinkage defect influence on the final properties to optimize composite cure schedule

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Russian Foundation for Basic Researches (grant 94-03-09235) during 1994 year.

REFERENCES

1. S. K. Gillham and J. B. Enns, On the cure and properties of thermosetting polymers using torsional braid analysis. *Trends in Polym. Sci.* **2**, 406-419 (1994).
2. A. R. Plepys and R. J. Farris, Evolution of residual stresses in three-dimensionally constrained epoxy resins. *Polymer* **31**, 1932-1936 (1990).
3. V. N. Korotkov, Yu. A. Chekanov and B. A. Rozenberg, Defect formation in curing epoxy in a rigid vessel. *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, **10**, 896-899 (1991).
4. D. Tabor. The bulk modulus of rubber. *Polymer*, **35**, 2795-2763 (1994).
5. Z. Cai and T. Gutowski, Winding and consolidation analysis for cylindrical composite structures. *J. Compos. Mater.*, **26**, 1374-1399 (1990).
6. Yu. A. Chekanov, L. M. Bogdanova, V. N. Korotkov, Scale factor in experimental model of high fiber content composite. *Mekhanika Kompozitnykh Materialov*, (1995, in press).
7. R. J. Farris and M. S. Vratsanos, Impulse viscoelasticity: a new method to study polymerization of thermosets. *Int. J. Fracture*, **39**, 93-102 (1989)
8. G. H. Lindsey, Triaxial fracture studies. *J. Appl. Phys.*, **38**, 4843-4852 (1967).
9. S. L. Simon and J. K. Gillham, Thermosetting cure diagrams: calculation and application. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, **53**, 709-727 (1994).
10. Yu. A. Chekanov, V. N. Korotkov, B. A. Rozenberg, E. A. Dzhavadyan, L. M. Bogdanova, Yu. P. Chernov, and S. G. Kulichikhin. Influence of vitrification on defect formation during curing epoxies. *J. Mater. Sci.*, **28**, 3869-3873 (1993).
11. Yu. A. Chekanov, V. N. Korotkov, B. A. Rozenberg, Gh. A. Dzhavadyan, L. M. Bogdanova, Cure shrinkage defects in epoxy resins. *Polymer*, **26**, (1995, in press).
12. V. N. Korotkov, Yu. A. Chekanov, and B. A. Rozenberg, The flaws of shrinkage formed in the course of curing of polymer-based composites (review). *Polym. Sci.*, **36**, 684-693 (1994).
13. V. N. Korotkov, Yu. A. Chekanov, and B. A. Rozenberg, Modeling of fiber-matrix interaction in high fiber content composites. Second Moscow International Composite Conference, Moscow, 144-145 (1994).

